

ENHANCING COLLEGE ENGLISH USING WEB 2.0

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic has brought global concerns on the means of continuing the teaching and learning process among educational institutions. This called for innovative strategies to replace the traditional modes of instruction with more accessible, and available ones. Through this, the Philippines' initiative to improve English competency remains steadfast in the midst of these circumstances. This study was carried out to propose strategies for enhancing College English using Web 2.0. It determined students' performance in listening and speaking, and reading. It also identified the usability of selected social media sites (SMS) to college English. The study utilized a descriptive design of research with a researcher-made test and questionnaire as the main data gathering instruments. This study involved 207 students selected using purposive sampling along with the language instructors in the five campuses of Batangas State University. To analyze the data, the study employed weighted mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed that the respondents had an average performance in listening and speaking, and reading. In relation to the usability of the SMS to listening and speaking, data showed that the respondents participate in oral interaction best in Facebook (FB) while becoming confident in the various communicative situations in YouTube (YT). On the other hand, the usability of the SMS to reading exhibited that the respondents significantly discover and use new words in FB and YT. Data showed that FB and YT were moderately usable in the two learning areas however Instagram (IG) was usable to less extent. The proposed strategies created by the researcher were named BASICS, an acronym which means Background, About the Activity, Support Information, Instructional Tools and Platforms, Course of Action, and Suggested Rubric. It may undergo validation, review, and evaluation by authorities and other language instructors.

Keywords: College English; Web 2.0; Descriptive Design, weighted mean, and standard deviation; Philippines

